

D3.2 1st version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform

WP3 DIANA service platform design and
development

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Introduction

The main purpose of DIANA project is to implement a commercial service platform that will empower water authorities. That will be achieved via the services offered through the DIANA platform, namely: i) non-authorised illegal water abstractions; ii) drought monitoring; and iii) monitoring of the water framework directive.

In order for the platform to be successfully implemented, various activities took place in parallel in the various work packages. More specifically the work in WP1 defined the user requirements and helped in providing better quality of experience to the end users, while the work in WP2 set out the methodology to be followed. The outputs from both work packages are available in the respective deliverables and were incorporated in the work that was done within WP3 and can be found on the first deliverable *“D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification”*.

Having set out the overall architecture in D3.1, the objective of *“D3.2: 1st version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform”* is to showcase the final developed components. Within that framework, the first part of the document presents the different components of DIANA platform that were developed for the first release of the platform and based on the input that was received. As also indicated in the description of work, those components were the following: i) **DIANA API**; ii) **GIS dashboard**; iii) **Web Application**; and iv) **Mobile Application**. In addition, in the second part of the deliverable, the user roles, as identified in D3.1 are presented and following are the various interfaces developed. Finally, in the third and last part of the deliverable various testing activities are presented.

1. Components of DIANA platform

DIANA platform was built in coherence with the user requirements as described in D1.1 «Users' and stakeholders' requirements analysis», D1.2 «Report on co-creation outcomes» and D1.3 «Specifications of DIANA services», and the system architecture as described in D3.1 «Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification». That last deliverable explains the three layer logic that was followed to implement the DIANA logic: a) the spatial and data layer; b) the application layer; and c) the frontend layer (Figure 1). It also showcases the various technologies that were chosen for the implementation of the platform, derived from the respective specifications that were provided to the technical team.

Figure 1- DIANA architecture

The layers described in the architecture include the four components that were foreseen in the description of work. More specifically the application layer provides the **DIANA API (1.1)** as a communication mean to the outside world and the **DIANA** frontend clients. The spatial and data layer includes all the necessary data that are used to configure, and execute the **DIANA** services as well as their results saved in spatiotemporal databases. Finally, the frontend layer contains the other three foreseen components, namely the **GIS Dashboard / Web Application and the Mobile Application** all of which are the **DIANA** frontend clients, which provide the screens that the end users see and work with.

In the sub-sections below, each of the components are presented, along with a brief explanation of their role and how they fit in the **DIANA** service platform. Following the description of the components, the user roles of the system resulting from the work carried out for D3.1 and based on those the various dashboards that were developed for the **DIANA** services, accompanied by their functionalities, are briefly described.

The first release of the platform does not include all the functionality, since the technical (WP3), EO (WP2), and pilot teams (WP4) are still in close co-operation for developing and integrating in the platform some additional products for all three services. An upcoming version of this deliverable will provide an update on those, as well as the testing that was carried out for that new functionality.

1.1. DIANA API

DIANA platform was accommodated by a Restful Application Program Interface (API). The reasoning for such a choice is the fact that a REST architectural style makes it easier for various and different systems to communicate with each other, by providing a common set of standards between them. By using a Restful API the technical team also ensured the modularity of the platform because small parts of the API or system components can be replaced by others offering similar inputs/outputs without affecting the system. For example in such a system that uses an API, the clients, meaning the pieces that access one of the services from the server, and the server itself are independent, guaranteeing thus that changes in one cannot affect the other, making them modular and separate as well. At the same time a Restful API ensures that the application is also stateless, meaning that a computation is carried out without any dependencies from other events or interactions with the system (preceding or following) and that the process can always be initiated by defining all its inputs in one place.

In other words by using a Restful API the team made sure that the system is reliable, is performing quickly, it is scalable and all its components can be managed, updated and re-used without affecting the system as a whole, even during operation.

Figure 2 – Example of API

1.2. GIS dashboard

There were many reasons for developing a GIS dashboard and accompany it with the **DIANA** web application. Some of the most common needs underlying such a requirement are the following: i) one view of important and key information; ii) use the information for operations; iii) quickly match the changes in the view with incidents, events and/or activities that are taking place. Those were also the reasons why a GIS dashboard was developed within **DIANA** project.

More specifically in the case of **DIANA** some of the multiple visualizations that have to work together on a single screen and that the users want to monitor are:

- i) the irrigated and the non-irrigated areas;
- ii) the accumulated volume of water (yearly);
- iii) the crop types of the area of interest;
- iv) the water volume used per crop type;
- v) the average water used per month.

Some of this information is also depicted as layers in a map. Each layer contains a set of data that users have requested and is interactively displayed.

1.3. Web application

A web application was chosen for **DIANA** project in order for it to be easily distributable to many clients, since it does not require installations and only a single browser can be used, which exists in nearly all personal computers. Additionally computers that are used to access a web application only require a minimum of available resources, while other types of applications (e.g. desktop or server applications) would request significantly more available resources.

Apart from the above-mentioned benefits that a web application offers to the end user, there are also benefits for the provider of the service. Namely the development is focused on the parts of the application that are unique for the achievement of the goals of the end users, rather than on issues such as installations. That also allows for building a more flexible pricing model, and as a result a business model, that is based on a monthly or yearly fee like many other software as a service (SaaS) application, which is a very common scheme for such applications.

1.4. Mobile application

A mobile application was chosen for **DIANA** project as complementary to the web application functionality. A mobile application is designed to run in devices such as smartphones and tablets, with the main advantage being that it is portable and has integrated sensors that can be used (e.g. GPS, accelerometer, compass, camera etc). Mobile apps are usually individual software units that have limited functionality. The fact that the mobile app was chosen to be complementary in **DIANA**, was a strategic decision that takes advantage of the limitations and advantages that apps in have. For example the location feature is usually build into mobiles, because users have associated that feature with portable devices rather than with PCs or laptops.

The **DIANA** mobile application was created solely with the purpose of being used by the inspectors of each organization. Inspectors are responsible for the on-spot checks that verify whether there has been a non-authorized water abstraction to a particular parcel or not. By definition, if they want to automate the whole procedure and move away from older practices, they need a portable tool, i.e. a mobile. **DIANA** provides that tool. Water managers assign the parcels that they deem suspicious and inspectors use the app in order to upload reports and photos from the on spot check, which they share with water managers, in order for both to have an overview of the progress done in any case.

2. DIANA interfaces

The current chapter entails a presentation of the various roles and functionalities that resulted from analyzing the services and the user requirements in D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3 and that are included in D3.1. As mentioned in various occasions, work package three is in close co-operation with work packages one and four and all the work carried out in them. The dashboards that come out of the development process are an example of that co-operation. More input is provided by the users as the project progresses and is incorporated gradually in the platform. More information on that process is provided in the following chapter.

2.1. User roles

As indicated in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” **DIANAs’** main stakeholders were identified from the very beginning of the project and are mainly public authorities (ministries, national-, basin-, regional and local authorities) and collective entities. Taking into consideration the **DIANA** services, specific customer segments can be distinguished, such as:

- (i) irrigation water managers (e.g. within local/ regional public authorities, associations of irrigators, etc.) responsible for monitoring and inspecting the abstraction of water irrigation;
- (ii) authorities (national, regional or local) in charge of developing water/drought management plans and issuing relevant authorizations;
- (iii) authorities that collect water fees.

Based on this segmentation, three types of users were identified:

- the Administrator (A)
- the Water Managers (WM) and
- the Inspectors (I).

The responsibilities and actions of each of the user groups identified are described in detail in D3.1. A graphical representation of the organization and department hierarchy is showcased in the figure below.

Figure 3: Organization & Department hierarchy

Having recognized the various types of users and their respective roles, the following dashboards have been developed: i) administrator dashboard; ii) non authorized illegal abstraction dashboard; iii) drought monitoring dashboard; iv) water framework directive dashboard; and v) mobile application dashboard.

As showcased by the title the first dashboard addresses the role of the “Administrator” of the individual organization that is using **DIANA**. Via that dashboard Administrators are able to provide and/or revoke access to the different members of the organization. The following three dashboards are addressing the roles of “Water Managers”. Those are the key actors for using **DIANA** for performing their daily activities in a more efficient and easy way. “Water Managers” are responsible for monitoring illegal abstractions in their areas of responsibility, developing strategic plans for the use of water resources and revising them in extreme conditions such as drought, as well as for monitoring the implementation of the water framework directive.

2.2. Administrator and user dashboards

The main actions that were foreseen in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” (3.2.1. Administrative actions, p24) for the role of **DIANA** “Administrators” were the following: 1) administrators will be able to sign in to the DIANA “admin area”, they will need to use their username and password that they have created during signing up to **DIANA**; 2) administrators can create/update users, meaning that they can add a new user and assign a specific role (administrator/ water manager/ inspector) to them, depending on the actual role of the user in the organization; and 3) administrators can create/update organizations and departments and since there can be more than one organizations for an area and one or more departments per area, administrators are responsible for creating and managing the organizations, departments and users .

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D · I · A · N · A

Sign In

Email

Password

Remember me Forget Password?

Sign In

Don't have an account yet? **Sign Up**

Figure 4 – Administrator sign up/sign in page

Users

Dashboard / Users

test03 Current Year: 2017

Filter By:

Search:

Firstname	Lastname	Email	Status	Actions
Adelia	Olaason	tomypierce@example.org	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Alicia	Klein	nemablick@example.org	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Andro	Koisi	androskoisi@gmail.com	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Andreas	Koisi	andreas@droxis.gr	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Apostolos	Agrafiotis	agrafiotis.family@gmail.com	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Apostolos	Apostolakis	tolis1082@gmail.com	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Caleb	Breitenberg	lethal@4example.net	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Cristian	Meise	cristianmeise@yahoo.com	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Daniela	De Medici	daniela@demedici@gmail.com	Not Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑
Diana	User	platformusartester@gmail.com	Approved	✓ Ⓞ 🗑

Showing 1 to 10 of 38 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 Next

Organizations

Dashboard / Organizations

test03 Current Year: 2017

Search:

Name	Creation Date	Actions
Abashira	July 26, 02:87 20:07	Ⓞ 🗑
Alfredotown	July 19, 04:47 06:07	Ⓞ 🗑
Audleburgh	January 24, 05:25 04:01	Ⓞ 🗑
Connallyton	April 20, 12:50 22:04	Ⓞ 🗑
Dominmouth	December 31, 19:02 21:12	Ⓞ 🗑
Dorliffon	May 26, 05:53 16:05	Ⓞ 🗑
East Zeldo	November 37, 01:14 26:11	Ⓞ 🗑
Floridosido	April 7, 09:58 16:04	Ⓞ 🗑
Hjhhj	May 23, 20:18 17:05	Ⓞ 🗑
Hunkland	July 8, 10:51 10:07	Ⓞ 🗑

Showing 1 to 10 of 30 entries

Previous 1 2 3 Next

Figure 5 – Administrator dashboard

2.3. Non authorized illegal abstraction dashboard

The main actions that were foreseen in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” (3.2.1. Detection and Monitoring of non-authorized water abstraction, p16-19) for the role of **DIANA** “Water Managers” for them to detect and monitor non-authorized illegal abstractions that were developed for the first release of **DIANA** platform, were the following: 1) a crop classification map to classify and map agricultural land use; 2) an irrigation classification map to provide information regarding the detection of which agricultural areas have been irrigated in the region of interest; 3) a net irrigation water requirements time variant map (crop water consumption) to depict the quantity of water necessary for irrigation; 4) a crop evapotranspiration time variant map to provide estimates of crop evapotranspiration during the cultivation period; 5) a reference evapotranspiration time variant map to provide estimates of reference evapotranspiration during the cultivation period; 6) a static map with the differences between the net irrigation water requirement and the maximum allowance of irrigation water consumption volumes; 7) a static map with non-authorized abstractions; 8) irrigation scheduling time variant maps; 9) a chart with the time series of net irrigation water requirements; and 10) a chart with the time series of crop growth parameters.

Figure 6 – Water Abstractions dashboard: Crop classification layer on map

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Figure 7 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Irrigated areas layer on map

Figure 8 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Net irrigation requirements layer on map

Figure 9 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Crop evapotranspiration layer on map

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Figure 10 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Crop evapotranspiration layer on map & time variation slider

Figure 12 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Irrigated areas layer and water rights layer on map

Figure 11 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Net irrigation requirements layer on map & time variation slider

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Figure 13 – Water Abstractions dashboard: Statistics and charts

Figure 14 - Water Abstractions dashboard: Statistics and charts

2.4. Drought monitoring dashboard

The main actions that were foreseen in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” (3.2.2. Drought Monitoring and Seasonal Drought Forecasting, p20-22) for the role of **DIANA** “Water Managers” for them to forecast and monitor seasonal drought that were developed for the first release of **DIANA** platform, were the following: 1) drought time variant maps; 2) drought classification time variant maps; and 3) soil moisture deficit time variant maps.

Figure 15 – Drought monitoring dashboard: skin temperature

Figure 16 - Drought monitoring dashboard: soil moisture drought index

2.5. Water framework directive dashboard

The main actions that were foreseen in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” (3.2.3. Monitoring actions for the implementation of the WFD, p22-23) for the role of DIANA “Water Managers” for them to monitor the implementation of the water framework directive that were developed for the first release of DIANA platform, were the following: 1) a total reference evapotranspiration map; and 2) total recorded irrigation water time variant maps.

Figure 17 – WFD dashboard: Crop evapotranspiration layer and time variation slider

Figure 18 - WFD dashboard: Gross irrigation requirements layer and time variation slider

2.6. Mobile application dashboard

The main actions that were foreseen in “D3.1: Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” (3.3. Mobile Application, p24-25) for the role of **DIANA** “Inspectors” for checks of non-authorized water abstractions that were developed for the first release of **DIANA** mobile application, were the following: 1) inspectors will be able to sign in to the mobile application; 2) users can recover their account using their email; 3) users can logout from the mobile application; 4) inspectors can see the list of the unprocessed inspections; 5) inspectors can see the list of their active (in process) inspections; 6) inspectors can snap images from their mobile to upload in an inspection; and 7) inspectors can provide a water meter indication for an active inspection.

Figure 19 – Inspector dashboard

3. Web and mobile application testing

The web application scenery has evolved a lot during the last years, with applications becoming more and more elaborate, intuitive and in many cases complicated. An application has to respond to a number of criteria, in order to stay relevant to the market, amongst which the main are: to be informative; to be accessible and user friendly. Hence developing a new application has become a more complex process, since there are many factors that should be taken into consideration. As a result, in order to make sure that all the user requirements are actually met, the applications have to undergo testing.

But what exactly is testing? Software testing is an investigation conducted to provide stakeholders with information about the quality of the software product or service under test¹. More commonly, testing is carried out in website and web application for bugs² or issues³. Conducting those tests and making improvements on the system ensures its proper functioning. After the tests and the fixes made, the application is ready for the real-time users.

There are many methods that can be used for testing a web application and there are many checklists that could be chosen over others. Nevertheless, as previously mentioned two of the things that must remain as the focal points of that attempt are the User Interface and the functionality of the platform.

In **DIANA** the user requirements were the result of the co-creation process. The objective is to establish a sense or fact of co-ownership, which is an indispensable condition for true empowerment of stakeholders and for sustainable implementation (i.e., continuity of **DIANA** services beyond the project end) of any tool or measure. Therefore, users and other stakeholders in all pilot areas have been consulted from the very beginning of the project.

That “co-ownership” is transferred in work package four as well, were the pilots and the technical partners will co-evaluate both the results provided, as well as the platform. But before the co-evaluation of the results, internal testing before the first release was also conducted. The checkpoints that were used were the following: i) functionality testing; ii) usability testing; iii) compatibility testing; iv) performance testing; and v) security testing. In the following chapters each of those check points are examined separately, as well as the results for each one of them. As it will be observed most of the issues arose in the testing of the functionality of the system, as expected.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_testing

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_bug

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_project_management#Issue

3.1. Functionality testing

In the functionality testing all the *links, forms used for submitting or getting information, cookies* must be followed to verify they behave in the right manner. Those tests were followed manually by testers at the end of each sprint and only when no issues were found, a stable version was produced by the development team which could reach the production server and then be presented to the pilot users. As mentioned above **DIANA** has various dashboards that serve different functionalities that had to be tested.

In the “Administrator” dashboard for example, there are various links and forms that were checked. Once signed in in the system, the administrator lands in the dashboard where there is an overview of the approved users, the number of organizations under the area of jurisdiction, as well as the departments. Each of those “features” are linked with the responding tabs that are also available on the top of the page. Each one of them were tested in order to see whether a link was broken. On top of that the forms that were available in the different tabs of the dashboard for adding a new user, a new organization and/or a new department were also checked.

Figure 20 – Administrator dashboard

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In the “Water Manager” dashboard there are also various links and forms that were checked, as well as the database connection. Once signed in in the system, the water managers land in the non-authorized water abstractions. The dashboard entails a number of information that is important, in order for the managers to be able to monitor their areas of interest of possible abstractions. All the information is provided to the frontend layer through the application layer that hosts a number of services with different functionalities (Figure 1). The proper operation of the servers was tested, in order to ensure that the needed information was provided to the end user. That was also tested via the graphics and the map-layer functionality, by checking whether the graphics and the layers were providing the correct information. The correctness of those was checked directly by the EO and pilot teams, since they had the necessary know how and data, in order to verify what was provided via DIANA platform. In the case of the Spanish pilot of La Mancha, there was an important deviation in the information provided by the platform and the reference data that the pilot had at its disposal. In order to resolve that issue, the technical team was in close communication with the pilot and the technical supporting team there. Due to the high importance of the issue, it was prioritized and resources were dedicated for its resolution. Apart from that issue there were various other issues that were reported after the first release by the partner. An indicative list is included below in sub-chapter 3.7.Bugs and issues.

Figure 21 – Water managers dashboard

Apart from the water abstractions dashboard, the drought monitoring and water framework directive monitoring dashboards were also tested internally and then after the first release, by the partners as well, in order to ensure their proper functionality.

3.2. Usability testing

In the usability testing the interaction of the user with the system is measured in order for any weakness to be identified and corrected. One of the check points that fall under the usability testing is that of User Interface. As previously mentioned, User Interface is one of the most important parameters that come into place and make a solution relevant to the users and the market.

In order to ensure the usability of **DIANA's** interface, the users were reporting interfaces and label what they could not fully comprehend and also the product owners and the dev team that supported the process created notes of parts of **DIANA** that were not easy for the users to follow. Those notes were discussed and the following principles were extracted and used for the rest of the project:

- Automated unwanted workload: mental calculations, estimations and comparisons should be eliminated. In **DIANA** that was already identified as a user requirement. A GIS dashboard that contains various statistics, as well as a map with different layers is already developed. More specifically, as soon as users sign into the system, they are able to see all the necessary information that they need to have in their disposal in order to take any actions. For example they can see the irrigable and non-irrigable areas, the crop types of the area of interest, the monthly average aggregated water per crop type and other information that was deemed as necessary by users themselves during the co-creation process.
- Reduce uncertainty: meaning that all data are presented in a clear and obvious manner in order for them to be understandable by the users. As in the previous case, the way the data are presented, was decided by the users along with the EO and the technical team. An example is the values that are used for the areas of interest (hectares), as well as for the volume of water (cubic meters, millimeters).
- Fuse data: bring together different sets of data, from lower to higher level of data and combine them in a simple to understand way. **DIANA** is using both lower and higher level data. An example would be the earth observation data that are acquired through various sources and that if not processed, users may not be able to understand them. Through **DIANA** platform, data are transformed into valuable information for the users.

- Use names that are conceptually related to function: the names and labels that are used should be familiar and must be recognized easily by the end user. Having three different pilots that task turned to be quite challenging. The first issue that came up during the development phase, concerned the terminology used for the different products in the platform. The technical team had to work in close co-operation with both the EO team and the pilots in order to develop a commonly accepted terminology. That was subsequently used in the platform. The same pattern was followed for other issues that came up.
- Group data in consistently meaningful ways: meaning that there should be a logical categorization of the available data. In the case of DIANA that was a rather easy task, since all data are grouped per service: i) non-authorized water abstractions; ii) drought monitoring; and iii) monitoring of the water framework directive.
- Include in the displays only the information needed by the user at a given time: users need to see the information that will help them make a decision, rather than irrelevant information. As mentioned more than once, the functionality and features of DIANA platform were developed in close co-operation with the final users. All the information that is provided in all three dashboards of the services resulted from the co-creation process and it is the information that the users need, in order to make decisions and proceed with their respective actions.

3.3. Compatibility testing

In the case of compatibility testing, the main aim is to check how the web application works in different browsers, if there are issues with the functionality, if the UI is responsive and if everything that was foreseen is now implemented and presented accurately. Since the applications are very depended on the browsers, it is a very important aspect of testing.

DIANA web application was tested in different browsers and using different devices. In the most common browsers available (i.e chrome, firefox, safari) **DIANA** application was working properly, without any major issues. Nevertheless, both during the internal testing and the one carried out by the users, it was found out that the application was not responsive in early versions of Internet Explorer but it was working properly on Microsoft's latest browser called Edge. As the team progresses and adds new functionalities and features, the compatibility is being checked at all times. The issue that came up and concerns the compatibility of the application with IE was added to the backlog of the team and is going to be resolved in later releases.

3.4. Performance testing

In the case of performance testing, what is being checked is the load and the stress that the application can withhold. Even though the application was not yet tested in real market conditions, with a heavy load of users making requests to the platform simultaneously, it should be noted that the team has foreseen the scalability of the platform and made the necessary arrangements for heavier load. More specifically, the team has selected a server with enough

space to ensure the handling of various requests at the same time and measured the performance there, in order to assure short response times with the maximum foreseen user load. The performance testing will be part of the next release and will only be verified when the product will be launched in the market.

3.5. Security testing

In that last aspect of testing, the security of the application is checked, in order to identify potential vulnerabilities of the system and repair them on a timely manner. Those vulnerabilities include: XSS, session hijacking and the use of unauthorized API calls.

3.6. Bugs and issues

The following table includes an indicative number of bugs and issues that were reported by users after the first release of the platform, as well as their prioritization by the technical team:

Bug/ Issue	Prioritization	Comments
Does not work in IE	Low	Not yet implemented
Language section must contain all the languages of DIANA	Low	To be implemented with localization of the platform
Statistics of La Mancha area are not correct	High	Not yet implemented
Values in the water abstraction service do not correspond to actual ones	High	High priority for pilots
Maps lack the legend of choosing a parameter	Medium	Already implemented from internal testing
Generating reports	Medium	Not yet implemented
Legend in water abstractions does not appear	High	High priority for pilots
Problem when uploading new areas/ boundaries	Medium	Guidelines to be issued, most probably issue with formats
Legends remain on the screen after un-selecting them	High	High priority for pilots
Mask of irrigated areas does not work	High	High priority for pilots
The months that match with the base google image are not the correct products	High	High priority for pilots
NIWR seems good in dates but the values are not corresponding in some cases	High	High priority for pilots

Table 1 – Bugs and issues

D3.2: 1st version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform

After the first release of the platform and the feedback received from the pilot partners, the technical team created a backlog with the bugs and issues that were reported. The prioritization was based on various criteria such as: i) importance for the pilot validation; ii) time and resources that required fixes and/or implementation; iii) effect on other components and/or functionalities of the system. The first of the criteria was the most important one, since it was the one to determine the unobstructed progress of the pilots towards the validation of the services. Following that prioritization, the team has proceeded in resolving various of the issues and resolving the bugs.

A worthy to mention example about the prioritization of the issues regards the third and fourth ones mentioned in the table above. One of the major issues that came up during implementation concerned the water abstractions dashboard of the pilot of La Mancha and more specifically the results provided by the platform. Both the technical and the pilot team of La Mancha dedicated a lot of time and a lot of effort in order to figure out the “glitch” in the system, going back and forth to the methodologies, the calculations and what was implemented. Nevertheless, the teams managed to resolve the issue and have the system ready for the pilots.

Apart from major issues that came up though, the team also tackled some issues that were not of the same importance, but they were resolved in order to help towards the better functioning of the platform. Such an example would be the issue with the legends that remained in the screen even after they were unselected.

4. Conclusions

As the project progresses, **DIANA** platform will also progress from an MVP to a fully functional service platform. The technical team keeps on working in close co-operation with the pilot teams and the EO team in order to resolve the issues and challenges that came up. The first year of development was mainly focused on streamlining the development and integration process, while the next year will be dedicated on building upon and enhancing the first version of the platform.

